

CORROSION STUDIES OF SELECTED FIBRE METAL LAMINATES WITH CARBON AND GLASS FIBRES

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1 Introduction

Composite materials have been developed in recent years. Actually, new generation of structural composite materials for technical applications are Fibre Metal Laminates (FML), consisting of alternating thin layers of metal sheets and fiber-reinforced composite material [1].

However, one of the most important issue of FML's for example with carbon fibres is corrosion behavior [2]. The reinforcing phase can enhance the physical and mechanical properties of the latter, however significantly changing its corrosion behaviour. The introduction of more noble reinforcing materials, such as carbon fibres, lead to the formation of galvanic couples causing corrosion [2-3]. The galvanic corrosion may considerably reduce the properties of FML's [2].

The present paper was focused on studying the corrosion behavior of FLM's based on aluminium alloy and titanium with carbon and glass fibres reinforced composite in typical corrosive environment.

2 Materials and methods

The FML laminates were prepared by stacking alternating layers of 2024T3 aluminium alloy with glass fiber/epoxy and carbon/epoxy prepregs (Hexcel Co.). The surface of aluminium sheets used in the production of FML laminates were pretreatment by anodizing in chromic acid and in the next stage the adhesive film-primer was applied. The FML composites has been produced by autoclave technique. For comparison FML's based on cp-Ti (grade 2) also was prepared.

The corrosion behaviour of the laminates was studied by the use of environmental chamber. The samples incubated in the solution of 5 wt.% NaCl (pH 7.0) at the 37°C and relative humidity (RH) of

95% for 6 weeks. Corrosion resistance of the laminates was determined by the mass loss method.

The corrosion resistance experiments were also carried out by accelerated electrochemical studies using the potentiodynamic method. The potentiodynamic measurements were made in the 3.5 wt.% NaCl aqueous solution.

The microstructure and surface morphology of FML's after corrosion tests with the use of stereoscopic and optical microscope were estimated.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 present typical structure of hybrid laminates with carbon (Al/CFRP) and glass fibres (Al/GFRP) after corrosion. The corrosion pits for both the Al/CFRP and Al/GFRP laminates are formed in the aluminium layers.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of Al/GFRP (top) and Al/CFRP (bottom) laminates after corrosion test.

It was observed that for Al/CFRP, the interface between metal and carbon fibre reinforced composite is characterized by the presence of numerous pits. It is reasonable to assume that the

presence of carbon fibres can increase the susceptibility to corrosion of FML's with aluminium sheets. The degradation of metal layers for Al/CFRP are significant and widespread. In the case of Ti/CFRP laminates the results indicated that the carbon fiber would not cause corrosion effects (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Microstructure of Ti/CFRP laminate after corrosion test.

The analysis of electrochemical corrosion properties also indicate the highest corrosion resistance of Ti/CFRP. In the case of hybrid laminates with aluminium, the susceptibility of Al/CFRP to corrosion is greater than the Al/GFRP.

It's a well-known fact, that corrosion resistance is higher along with the increase of surface homogeneity of materials. Moreover, certain factors influencing corrosion of the composites include microporosity and voids at the interface, and the presence of residual stresses [3-5]. The presence of reinforcing phase is the main factor causing higher susceptibility to corrosion of composites. The introduction of more noble reinforcing materials, such as carbon fibres (very efficient cathode) with active aluminium alloy lead to the formation of galvanic couples favourable to corrosion [9,10]. The of essential issue is presence of high electrical conductivity phase – carbon fibres at the metal/composite interface. Therefore, contact between carbon fiber composites and metals with similar properties in an electrolyte such as rain or seawater will be extremely undesirable [11]. In normal exploitation such corrosion is often unnoticeable. It is manifested only when damage is serious enough to make further exploitation impossible. The protection of aluminium-composite interface (isolating the carbon fibres from the aluminium) is the important issue for corrosion behavior. A thermoplastic coating like PolyEtherImide (PEI), isolating the carbon prepreg with glass prepreg on both sides and hybrid sol-gel

coatings can improve the corrosion-resistance of FML's.

4. Summary

The microstructural and corrosion analysis for fibre metal laminates reinforced carbon fibres demonstrated the complexity of degradation process and its mechanisms in the structure of laminates. The conducted examinations can indicate the influence of carbon fibres on the increase of susceptibility to corrosion, due to galvanic couples between aluminium and carbon fibres. However, hybrid laminates consisting of titanium and carbon reinforced composite layers exhibited superior galvanic corrosion resistance. It seems necessary to conduct further investigation in the field of corrosion behavior of FML's.

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References

- [1] A. Vlot, JW. Gunnink “*Fiber Metal Laminates: An Introduction*”. Kluwer Academic Publishers L.B: Dordrecht, 2001.
- [2] WX. Wang, Y. Takao, T. Matsubara “Galvanic corrosion-resistant carbon fiber metal laminataes”. *Proceedings of 16th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Kyoto, Japan , July 8-13, 2007.
- [3] LH. Hihara, RM Latanision ”Galvanic corrosion of aluminium matrix composites. *Corrosion*, Vol. 48, No. 7, pp. 546-552, 1992.
- [4] ND. Alexopoulos, ChJ. Dalakouras, P. Skarvelis, SK. Kourkoulis “Accelerated corrosion exposure in ultra thin sheets of 2024 aircraft aluminium alloy for GLARE applications”. *Corrosion Science*, Vol. 55, pp.289–300, 2012.
- [5] A. Gebhard, T. Bayerl, AK. Schlarb, K. Friedrich “Increased wear of aqueous lubricated short carbon fiber reinforced Polyetheretherketone (PEEK/SCF) composites due to galvanic fiber corrosion”. *Wear*, Vol. 268, pp. 871–876, 2010.
- [6] Z Peng, X. Nie “Galvanic corrosion property of contacts between carbon fiber cloth materials and typical metal alloys in an aggressive environment”. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2012.08.098>.